

THERMAL EFFECTS AND HIGH TEMPERATURE BEHAVIOR OF METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

Enayat Mahajerin, Mechanical Engineering Department,
Saginaw Valley State University, University Center, MI 48710

Gary Burgess, School of Packaging
Michigan State University, East Lansing, MI 48823

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ABSTRACT- The pervasive trend since the 1980's was to use metal matrix composites (MMC's) instead of steels. This was done to reduce weight, increase strength, improve wear resistance, and reduce thermal distortion. MMC's are manufactured by adding ceramic particles to metals (dispersion strengthening). Today, MMC's are used in the auto industry, the military, and for certain space applications. The commercial use of MMC's includes various machine components such as aluminum pistons reinforced with alumina in some diesel engines. When such composites are subjected to high processing temperatures or when they are used at elevated service temperatures, peak temperatures will be needed to assess thermal stresses and dimensional stability of the component. This requires an accurate evaluation of the time dependent temperature field within the component.

We consider a crankshaft made of an MMC subjected to combined bending and twisting while rotating in an ambient environment where temperature can be high. The temperature rise in the shaft due to operation in a hot environment and also because of heat generation as a result of material damping is determined using an explicit finite difference method (FDM). The peak temperature is used to investigate the internal state of stress at the interface between the particle and matrix. The method is efficient, relatively easy to program, and can be modified for other geometries and boundary conditions. Examples are used to investigate the behavior of typical MMC's.

INTRODUCTION

Metal Matrix Composites (MMC's) are now beginning to make a significant contribution in construction and industrial practices [1,2,3]. The matrix is normally a ductile metal whereas the reinforcing constituent is a stiff, load-bearing ceramic in the form of monofilament, whiskers, or particles. Active research has concentrated on the elasticity and manufacturing aspects of MMC's. However, central to the understanding of the mechanical behavior of MMC's is their thermal behavior. Since MMC's are made of metal (the matrix) and ceramics (reinforcements), a temperature change will create stresses at the interface between the ceramic particle and the matrix because of different thermal expansion coefficients. These temperature-dependent internal stresses can reduce the material strength and therefore weaken the MMC.

The reinforcement particles or fibers can be regarded as inhomogeneities in a homogeneous matrix. An increase in temperature causes the matrix to expand more than the particles because the coefficient of expansion for the matrix is usually larger than that for the particle. Consequently the matrix wants to pull away from the particle. If the adhesion between the two is strong enough, it cannot, and so the matrix exerts a tensile stress on the surface of the particle and vice-versa.

We consider a typical crankshaft made of MMC's in which the operating force is chosen so that the resulting stresses under maximum rpm are appropriate for the material strength. The load can cause the shaft to bend and twist and as a result, every element of the shaft generates heat due to material damping. The amount of heat generation is evaluated from the strain energy density and the loss factor [4]. The strain energy density for a shaft subjected to bending and torsion is well known from elementary mechanics, and values of loss factors for different materials are available [5].

FORMULATION

The particular problem to be studied here is the rotating crankshaft shown in Figure 1. The governing transient heat conduction equation with heat generation in an anisotropic material in cylindrical coordinates is [6],

$$\frac{k_r}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{k_\theta}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial \theta^2} + k_z \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial z^2} + \dot{q} = \rho_c c_c \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} \quad (1)$$

where

- $T(r, \theta, z, t)$** : Time-dependent temperature function
- k_r, k_θ, k_z** : Thermal conductivities
- ρ_c** : Mass density of the composite
- c_c** : Specific heat of the composite
- \dot{q}** : Heat generation (due to material damping)

The initial conditions, boundary conditions, and symmetry conditions are:

$$\text{Initial Condition:} \quad T(r, \theta, z, 0) = T_i \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Boundary Conditions:} \quad T(R, \theta, z, t) = T_s \quad (3)$$

Insulated ends

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial z} = 0, \quad \text{at } z=0, L \quad (4)$$

HEAT GENERATION: The heat generation term in Eq. 1 is obtained from the strain energy density and the loss factor. The strain energy density, u , of the shaft under combined bending and torsion is [4]:

$$\mathbf{u} = \frac{\sigma_z^2}{2E_z} + \frac{\tau^2}{2G_z} \quad (5)$$

where E and G are the elastic modulus and shear modulus, respectively, and

$$\tau = \frac{T r}{J} = \frac{(F a \cos \alpha) r}{\pi R^4 / 2} \quad (6)$$

$$\sigma_z = \frac{M y}{I} = \frac{F(L-z) r \sin(\alpha + \theta)}{\pi R^4 / 4} \quad (7)$$

Substitution of (6) and (7) into (5) gives

$$\mathbf{u}(r, \theta, z, t) = \frac{2}{\pi R^8} F^2 r^2 \left[\frac{4(L-z)^2 \sin^2(\omega t + \theta)}{E_z} + \frac{a^2 (\cos^2 \omega t)}{G_z} \right] \quad (8)$$

where α is the angle the crank makes with the horizontal axis, and ω (rad/s) is the angular velocity of the shaft.

Eqn. (8) is the strain energy density at the material point (r, θ, z) at time t. The average value of the strain energy density over time will be used to determine the heat generation,

$$\bar{\mathbf{u}} = \mathbf{u}(r, \theta, z) = \frac{2}{\pi R^8} F^2 r^2 \left[\frac{4(L-z)^2}{E_z} I_1 + \frac{a^2}{G_z} I_2 \right] \quad (9)$$

where

$$I_1 = \lim_{t_f \rightarrow \infty} \int_0^{t_f} \sin^2(\omega t + \theta) dt = \frac{1}{2} \quad (10)$$

$$I_2 = \lim_{t_f \rightarrow \infty} \int_0^{t_f} (\cos^2 \omega t) dt = \frac{1}{2} \quad (11)$$

Therefore, Eqn. (9) becomes

$$\bar{\mathbf{u}} = \mathbf{u}(r, z) = \frac{F^2 r^2}{\pi R^8} \left[\frac{4(L-z)^2}{E_z} + \frac{a^2}{G_z} \right] \quad (12)$$

Note that Eqn. (12) is no longer a function of θ . This simplifies the analysis considerably. The heat generation rate at location (r, θ, z) is

$$\dot{q} = \frac{u_d}{t_c} \quad (13)$$

where u_d is the heat dissipation per cycle and t_c is the cycle time,

$$t_c = \frac{2\pi}{\omega} \quad (14)$$

where ω is related to the shaft rpm, n , through

$$\omega = \frac{2\pi n}{60} \quad (15)$$

Because $u = \cos^2 \omega t$, we can write its average value as,

$$\bar{u} = \frac{1}{2} u_{\text{peak}} \quad (16)$$

Therefore,

$$\dot{q} = 2\omega \gamma \bar{u} \quad (17)$$

Substitution of (16) into (17) and the result into (12) we obtain

$$\dot{q} = \frac{n\gamma}{15\pi} \frac{F^2 r^2}{R^8} \left[\frac{4(L-z)^2}{E_z} + \frac{a^2}{G_z} \right] \quad (18)$$

NUMERICAL PROCEDURE

Since the problem is axisymmetric, the Eq. 1 becomes:

$$k_r \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial r^2} + \frac{k_r}{r} \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} + k_z \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial z^2} + \dot{q} = \rho_c c_c \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} \quad (19)$$

An explicit finite difference version of Eq. (19) can be established by subdividing the rectangle R by L into

small meshes combined with a suitable time step Δt to ensure stability [7],

$$\Delta t \leq \frac{a^2 b^2}{2(b^2 \alpha_x + a^2 \alpha_y)} \quad (20)$$

where

$$\alpha_x = \frac{k_x}{\rho_c c_c}, \quad \alpha_y = \frac{k_y}{\rho_c c_c} \quad (21)$$

in which k is the material conductivity, ρ is density, and c is the specific heat. The subscript “c” denotes composite. Material properties are evaluated as follows [3]:

$$k_c = v_p k_p + (1-v_p) k_m \quad (22)$$

$$E_c = v_p E_p + (1-v_p) E_m \quad (23)$$

$$\rho_c = v_p \rho_p + (1-v_p) \rho_m \quad (24)$$

$$c_c = [v_p \rho_p c_p + (1-v_p) \rho_m c_m] / \rho_c \quad (25)$$

$$(E\gamma)_c = v_p (E\gamma)_p + (1-v_p) (E\gamma)_m \quad (26)$$

In these expressions subscripts p and m denote “*particulate*,” and “*matrix*,” respectively.

THERMAL STRESSES: Different coefficients of thermal expansion for the matrix and the particulate leads to volume strains induced by the temperature increase ΔT . Pertinent coefficients of thermal expansion are listed in [1]. We consider a particle-reinforced MMC in which the particle is modeled as a spherical inclusion. The radial displacements for the particle and for the matrix when an applied tensile stress σ acts in combination with the temperature change ΔT is obtained from elasticity theory [8],

$$u_p = (1-2\nu_p) R \frac{\sigma}{E_p} + \alpha_p \Delta T R \quad (27)$$

$$u_m = -\frac{1}{2} (1+\nu_m) R \frac{\sigma}{E_m} + \alpha_m \Delta T R \quad (28)$$

The compatibility condition, $u_p = -u_m$, leads to

$$\sigma = \frac{(\alpha_m - \alpha_p)\Delta T}{\frac{1 + \nu_m}{E_m} + \frac{1 - 2\nu_p}{E_p}} \quad (29)$$

This is the tensile stress at the interface between the particle and matrix due to a temperature rise.

EXAMPLES

The following examples illustrate applications of the method in the practices associated with the MMC shafts. Two shafts made of different MMC's (Al-Al₂O₃ and Al-Sic) were used in these examples. Material properties are available in [1] and are shown in Tables 1 and 2. Summary of the results are shown in Figures 2,3, and 4.

Figure 2: Shows the time needed for the minimum temperature of each MMC to reach the ambient temperature, T_a .

Figure 3: Show maximum possible temperatures corresponding to different loss factors.

Figure 4. Shows the maximum interface stress due to temperature rise. The results can be used as measure of degradation of the MMC as a result of thermal effects.

The following numerical data were used in the examples:

Shaft length: $L=0.0762$ m, Shaft Diameter: $D=0.0254$ m, Crank length: $a=0.0508$ m,

Initial temperature: $T_i=60$ °F, Ambient temperature: $T_a=105$ °C,

Volume fractions of the reinforcements: $0.1 \leq \nu_p \leq 0.4$,

Loss factor: $0.05 \leq \gamma \leq 0.2$,

Shaft speed, n : 4000 rpm

CONCLUSIONS

The behavior of components made of MMC's is often sensitive to temperature because changes in temperature can cause internal stresses as a result of differential thermal contraction between the matrix and the reinforcements. The paper describes an efficient method to investigate these effects in shafts made of different MMC's. The effects of heat generation due to material damping is also included in the computation of the temperature rise. Results show that in addition to the mechanical and physical properties, peak temperatures have profound effects on the interface stresses which can weaken the mechanical properties of the component.

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Table 1. Mechanical Properties.

Composite	ρ kg/m ³	E GPa	ν	G GPa
Al	2800	70	0.33	26.3
Al ₂ O ₃	3960	379	0.24	157.2
SiC	3170	616	0.17	300

Table 2. Thermal Properties.

Material	α m/m-°C	k W/m-°C	c_p J/kg-°C
Al	23.6x10 ⁻⁶	171	896
Al ₂ O ₃	8.8x10 ⁻⁶	30	710
SiC	4.3x10 ⁻⁶	25	690

Figure 2- Time to Reach the Ambient Temperature.

Figure 3- Max Temperatures for Different Reinforcement Content (%).

Figure 4- Effects of Temp. Change on the MMC Strength.